

The Effect of Work Motivation, Additional Income for Employees (TPP), and Organizational Commitments on the Work Commitments of Civil Servants Agency of South Sulawesi Province

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Abstract:-The purpose of this study was to examine and explain the effect of work motivation, provision of additional employee income (TPP), and organizational commitment on the work commitment of civil servants at the regional civil service agency of Southeast Sulawesi province. This research design is based on a quantitative approach with a positive paradigm using an instrument in the form of a questionnaire to all employees at the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province as many as 126 people. The analytical tool used in testing the hypothesis of this research is multivariate regression analysis. The results of this study indicate that work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work commitment, the provision of additional employee income has a positive and significant effect on work commitment while organizational commitment has a positive but not on work commitment. Simultaneously research on work motivation, providing additional employee income and organizational commitment have a positive and significant effect on employee commitment. Thus, it can be concluded that changes in the increase in work motivation which are reflected through the provision of imbalance, additional income and organizational commitment have a positive and significant contribution to work commitment through engagement and work involvement.

Keywords:- Work Motivation, Provision of Additional Employee Income, Organizational Commitment, Work Commitment.

I. INTRODUCTION

Quality human resources are an asset of an organization because human resources are the driving force of the organization in achieving its goals. In order to achieve the goals of the organization, it is necessary to manage and manage its human resources, so that human resources want to work optimally. Every organization expects to achieve its goals and achieve success. To achieve this, organizations need quality human resources. Human resources will be qualified if they at least have the necessary competencies to carry out their

duties. However, competence alone is not enough to make an organization successful.

Dessler, G., & Varrkey, (2005) put forward the definition of human resources stating that: " *Human Resource Management (HRM) is the police and practices involved in carrying the "people" or human resource aspect of a management position including recruiting, screening, training, rewarding and appraising*". Based on this definition, it can be concluded that human resource management is one part of management studies that focuses on how to attract, hire, train, motivate, and process to acquire, train, assess, and compensate employees in order to achieve organizational goals.

The achievement of the goals of the organization cannot be separated from the work of all components of human resources in the organization. In achieving these goals, organizations are required to have productive and highly committed human resources. Employee commitment is very important and needed by all organizations in the world.

The role of apparatus resources is a very important element in the sustainability of government life and development. The apparatus resources are the domain of Civil Servants. The main highlight is the creation of *good and clean governance* making the role of Civil Servants. need serious attention.

Meyer, et al (1993) suggested that employees who have a strong level of commitment are the last to leave the organization. In addition, employees who are committed and satisfied and who identify with the goals and values of the organization are human resources that can be used to improve organizational performance and make the organization achieve organizational goals.

Employees who have a high work commitment to the organization, will show positive attitudes and behaviors in their organization, employees will have a sense of defending their organization, always be active in achieving to improve performance, and have definite confidence in helping achieve organizational goals.

Some of the factors that are thought to be very influential on the work commitment of an employee include work motivation factors, compensation factors and organizational commitment owned by the employee concerned. Allen, N., (1990) formulate a definition of organizational commitment as a psychological construct that is characteristic of the relationship between organizational members and their organization and has implications for individual decisions to continue their membership in the organization. Based on this definition, it can be concluded that members who are committed to their organization will be more can survive as part of the organization than members who are not committed to the organization. Commitment means a strong individual acceptance of the company's goals and values, where the individual will try and work and have a strong desire to stay in the company.

Colquitt, et.al, (2009) suggests that *Organizational commitment is defined as the desire on the part of an employee to remain a member of the organization. Organizational commitment influences whether an employee stays a member of the organization (is retained) or leaves to pursue another job (turns over).*

Based on the description above, it can be explained that *organizational commitment* is an attitude of accepting the values and goals of the organization, showing a willingness to advance the organization, staying a member of the organization most of the formatting specifications needed for preparing electronic versions of their papers. All standard paper components have been specified for three reasons: (1) ease of use when formatting individual papers, (2) automatic compliance to electronic requirements that facilitate the concurrent or later production of electronic products, and (3) conformity of style throughout a conference proceedings. Margins, column widths, line spacing, and type styles are built-in; examples of the type styles are provided throughout this document and are identified in italic type, within parentheses, following the example. Some components, such as multi-leveled equations, graphics, and tables are not prescribed, although the various table text styles are provided. The formatter will need to create these components, incorporating the applicable criteria that follow.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Work Commitment*

Work commitment (*work/job commitment*) is one form of individual work attitudes in organizations which has become one of the important emphasis in the *human relations school of thought*, Fornes and Rocco, (2011). Becker (1960), Blau & Boal, (1987), Cohen, (1999) stated that commitment is an important predictor such as *turnover intentions* of employees, performance, job satisfaction, pro-social *behavior*, absenteeism levels, and employee inaction at work (*tardiness*).

Commitment is one of the keys that determine the success or failure of an organization in achieving its goals. Employees who are committed will usually show a work attitude that is attentive to their duties and has a sense of responsibility in carrying out the assigned tasks. According to Meyer, et.al, (1993) stated that *Commitment as the degree of pledging or binding of the individual to a set of behaviors and motivates one to act* ", which can be interpreted that commitment is a dedication or sense of emotional attachment which is manifested through motivation and behavior. someone to do something. The term "something" in this context can refer to an organization, work unit, work team, or task/job .

Work commitment has a relatively broad scope, so that it often gives rise to multiple interpretations. Morrow (1993) in Cohen (1999) states that one of the main problems or problems in commitment research is that in addition to its broad scope, each component included in it can *overlap* one another. Therefore, Mohsan et al., (2011) summarizes the definition of work commitment, namely *Employee commitment is the loyalty and support of workforce to the goals of organization* (James P. Begin, 1997). *It is in fact an employee's orientation towards the organization in terms of his loyalty and involvement in the* (Robbins dan Coulter, 1999). *Employee commitment as an extent to which an employee identifies and is involved with his organization or is unwilling to leave it* ((Greenberg, J. and Baron, 2000)).

Then Rabinowitz (1977) in Fornes, and Rocco, (2011) provide a definition of work commitment, namely: *Job commitment is the degree to which a person identifies psychologically with his/her work and the degree to which one's work performance affects one's self-esteem. and self-image.* Furthermore, Van den Berg (2011) characterizes work commitment from the magnitude of one's emotional attachment and dedication to the task and to the organization known as work engagement. Therefore, work commitment can be recognized and measured through indicators: (1) the level of employee work involvement in the task Price (1997); (Gary J. Blau and Kimberly B. Boal, 1987) and (2) *work engagement* (Van den Berg (2011); (Wiley, J. W., Kowske, B. J., & Herman, 2010)).

➤ *Work motivation*

Work motivation is defined as an activity or behavior that can lead to, channel, maintain and encourage a person's behavior to work as well as possible in accordance with the duties and work he has.

According to Ott, (1996), the four basic premises of Maslow's hierarchy of needs are as follows:

1. All humans have needs which underlie their motivational structure;
2. As lower levels of needs are satisfied, they no longer 'drive' behavior;
3. Satisfied needs are not motivators; and
4. As lower level needs of workers become satisfied, higher order needs take over as the motivating forces”.

Herzberg, (1968) grouped motivation into two theory factors, namely *satisfiers motivators* (abbreviated *motivators*) and *dissatisfiers. hygiene factors* (abbreviated as *hygiene factors*) , namely the theory applied in the work environment that discusses human motivation in the work environment and the impact on job satisfaction and mental health of each worker. According to Herzberg (1968) *dissatisfiers hygiene factors* are factors that cause dissatisfaction in employees while *satisfiers motivators* are a group of factors that encourage and stimulate employees to work better and productively. These factors include:

- 1) *Achievement*
- 2) *Recognition*
- 3) *work-itself*
- 4) *responsibility*
- 5) *advancement* .

➤ *Additional Employee Income (TPP)*

Additional Employee Income (TPP) is a compensation provided by the organization to its employees with the aim of helping to build, maintain and strengthen the expectations of employees so that in them there will be greater morale, work motivation and discipline to participate for the organization in realizing organizational success.

According to Dessler, (2005) suggests that " *compensation as all forms of payments or rewards given to employees which arise from their employment*", which can be interpreted that compensation is all forms of payments or rewards given to employees arising from their work. So that compensation is one of the basic reasons for employees to look for work. Mathis Robert, (2002) divide compensation into two groups, namely direct compensation and indirect compensation. Furthermore, direct compensation consists of basic salary and variable salary. Meanwhile, indirect compensation is in the form of allowances.

Dessler, (2017) states that one of the bases in providing compensation to employees or employees is based on *equity theory* or the theory of justice that is *external equity, internal equity, individual, and procedural equity*. This *equity theory* reveals that people are satisfied or not depending on the presence or absence of justice in a work situation. According to this theory, the main components in the theory of justice are

inputs, outcomes of justice, and injustice. Inputs are valuable factors for employees who are considered to support their work, such as education, experience, skills, number of tasks, and equipment used to do their work.

Therefore, the basis for providing compensation is the fulfilment of a sense of justice for all employees. This sense of justice is not only based on the severity or lightness of tasks, challenges or work risks, task performance (*internal equity*) but is also based on the employee's perception after comparing the compensation he received by his co-workers in one work unit, another work unit and the compensation received. by employees in other agencies (*external equity*) .

Based on Dessler (2017) explanation of the theory of justice, the measurement of financial compensation in the form of additional employee income (TPP) in the context of this study is based on employee perceptions of the two bases of compensation justice which are components in this study, namely:

- 1) *external equity component*.
- 2) *internal equity component*.

➤ *Organizational Commitment*

Organizational commitment defined by Mowday, et al (1979)) suggests that organizational commitment shows strong belief and support for the values and goals (goals) to be achieved by the organization. Then according to Steers (1988) stated that organizational commitment explains the relative strength of an individual identification with involvement in an organization.

According to (Porter, et al (1974) commitment is the strength of a person's recognition and involvement in a particular organization. Then Becker, (1960) describes organizational commitment as a tendency to be bound in a consistent line of activities because it considers the costs of carrying out other activities (stopping work).

Meyer, et al (1993) suggest that organizational commitment as a psychological construct which is characteristic of the relationship between organizational members and their organization and has implications for individual decisions to continue membership in the organization. This organizational commitment is grouped by Allen, N., (1990) into 3 (three) sub-indicators, namely:

- 1) *affective commitment*;
- 2) *continuance commitment (continuance commitment)*;
- 3) *normative commitment (normative commitment)*.

Fig 1
Conceptual framework of the effect of work motivation, giving TPP and organizational commitment to work commitment

Based on the description of the literature review, the results of previous research and the conceptual framework, this hypothesis is:

- Hypothesis 1: Work Motivation, Provision of TPP and Organizational Commitment simultaneously have a positive and significant effect on the work commitment of Civil Servants of the Regional Personnel Agency of Prov. Southeast Sulawesi
- Hypothesis 2: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on the work commitment of Civil Servants at the Provincial Civil Service Agency. Southeast Sulawesi
- Hypothesis 3: The provision of TPP has a positive and significant effect on the work commitment of Civil Servants at the Provincial Civil Service Agency. Southeast Sulawesi
- Hypothesis 4: Organizational Commitment has a positive and significant effect on the work commitment of Civil Servants at the Provincial Civil Service Agency. Southeast Sulawesi.

III. METHODS

This research belongs to the category of survey research / direct observation in the field with the aim of confirming the predictions made and explaining based on facts or circumstances in the field. Explanatory research aims to obtain appropriate testing in drawing conclusions that are causal between variables and hypothesis testing and then choosing alternative actions (Kuncoro, 2003). The population in this study were all Civil Servants at the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province, totaling 126 people. The research sample taken is Permanent Employees (PNS) totaling 126 people. Because all members of the population are sampled, this study is a census. Thus, the sample calculation process does not need to be carried out (Arikunto, 2002). The analytical tool used in testing the hypothesis of this research is multivariate regression analysis.

IV. RESULT

The summary of the results of the multiple linear regression analysis in this study can be seen in the table below:

Table 1
Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Results

Variable Model		Standardized coefficients beta (β)	Sig.-t	Information
X	Y			
Motivation (X ₁)	Work Commitment (Y)	0.195	0.038	Significant
Giving TPP (X ₂)	Work Commitment (Y)	0, 323	0.001	Significant
Organizational Commitment (X ₃)	Work Commitment (Y)	0, 122	0.199	Not significant
Constant Value		14,891		

Source: Primary data, processed by Researchers 2022

Furthermore, to find out the correlation/relationship between independent variables, namely work motivation (X1), TPP (X2) and organizational commitment (X3) with work commitment (Y), it can be seen based on the results of the Summary Model test in table 2 as follows:

Table 2
Model Summary Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.626 ^a	.477	.459	3.885

a. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Commitment, Tpp, Motivation

b. Dependent Variable: Work Commitment

Source: Primary data, processed by Researchers 2022

Furthermore, to see the simultaneous influence of work motivation variables, giving TPP and organizational commitment to the work commitment of Civil Servants of the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. It can be seen from the results of the F test in table 3 as follows:

Table 3
F-Test Results (ANOVA^a)
ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1 Regression	705,337	3	235,112	15.575	.000 ^b
Residual	1841,592	122	15,095		
Total	2546,929	125			

a. Dependent Variable: Work Commitment

b. Predictors: (Constant), Organizational Commitment, TPP, Motivation

Source: Primary data, processed by Researchers 2022

V. DISCUSSION

➤ *The Effect of Motivation, Additional Employee Income (TPP) and Organizational Commitment on Work Commitment*

There is a simultaneous positive and significant effect between work motivation, giving TPP and organizational commitment and has a positive and significant effect on employee work commitment at the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. = 0.05, then the sig value of the F-Test result is smaller than = 0.05. In other words, increased motivation, perceptions of Additional Employee Income (TPP) and Organizational Commitment together collaborate and support each other so as to increase employee work involvement in carrying out their duties, causing employee work commitment to increase.

This is supported by the theory put forward by (Porter, L. W., Steers, R. M., Mowday, R. T., & Boulian, 1974); Mowday, R.T, Porter, (1982) and the second method proposed by (Becker, 1960). According to (Mowday, R.T, Porter, 1974)

commitment is the strength of a person's recognition and involvement in a particular organization. Or organizational commitment as the degree to which employees identify with the organization and their involvement in a particular organization Mowday, R.T, Porter, (1982). On the other hand, Becker, (1960) describes commitment as a tendency to be bound in a consistent line of activities because of the perceived costs of carrying out other activities (stopping work). This theory is also supported by research conducted by (Vivian et al., 2019). The results of this study indicate that there is a significant relationship between work engagement and organizational commitment and vice versa.

➤ *The Effect of Motivation on Work Commitment*

Work motivation partially has a positive and significant effect on employee work commitment at the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province The results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the variable of work motivation, when compared with a significance level of = 0.05. Therefore The significant value of the t-test result < = 0.05 can be interpreted that the second hypothesis partially proposed in this study is proven to be acceptable.

This shows that if the motivation increases, it causes employee work commitment to also increase, this means that employees who have high motivation to carry out tasks will also have a high intensity of work involvement in their duties and functions in their work units. The results of this study are supported by the results of previous studies including the findings of (Sharma & Bhati, 2017), (Watson et al., 2018), (Olaajo et al., 2017) and (Widagdo, A., Widodo, D., & Samosir, 2018) proving that work motivation has an influence positive and significant to work commitment

➤ *The Effect of Giving TPP on Work Commitment*

Provision of Additional Employee Income (TPP) partially has a positive and significant effect on employee work commitment at the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. The results of multiple linear regression analysis showed that the variable of providing additional employee income (TPP), when compared with a significance level of = 0.05. Thus, the significant value of the t-test < = 0.05 can be interpreted that the third hypothesis partially proposed in this study is proven to be acceptable.

This shows that if the employee's evaluative perception of the fairness of the additional income allowance as part of the compensation he receives increases , it will have an impact on increasing emotional involvement in the implementation of tasks at the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province . The results of this study are supported by the results of previous studies including research conducted by (Enriko, 2020), (Jennifer Nageli Koitalek, 2017) proving that the provision of Additional Employee Income (TPP) has a positive and significant effect on employee work commitment.

➤ *The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Work Commitment*

The organizational commitment variable partially has a positive and insignificant effect on the work commitment of employees at the Regional Personnel Board of Southeast Sulawesi Province. The results of multiple linear regression analysis showed organizational commitment variable, when compared with a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$. Thus the significant value of the t-test results $t > 0.05$ can be interpreted that the fourth hypothesis partially proposed in this study is proven to be rejected. This indicates that if Organizational Commitment has increased, it has not significant enough effect on increasing employee work commitment, this means that although employee organizational commitment has increased, it does not affect the increase in work commitment, in this case, employee participation in carrying out organizational tasks in realizing organizational success has not increased. This is because even though employees experience feelings/emotional attachments to the institution where they work and the attachment of their thoughts and needs to keep working at their organizations increases, it does not increase pride, satisfaction, loyalty, and a sense of emotional attachment of employees to their work units as well as the attention, desire, and willingness of employees. to always be united and involved in their duties.

These results are in line with research conducted by (Satata, 2020) which shows the results that *organizational commitment* has no significant effect on *work engagement* in workers in the field of information technology development. This is also supported by the results of research conducted by (Ortiz et al., 2013) that *organizational commitment* has a negative effect on *work engagement*. Based on this, it indicates that the influence of the organization does not have a positive effect on some individuals, it can be explained that each individual prefers to develop themselves into *freelancers* without being bound by the organization.

VI. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Based on the results of research and discussion, it can be concluded that work motivation, Provision of Additional Employee Income (TPP) and Organizational Commitment simultaneously affect the Work Commitment of the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. This means that employees who have internal encouragement (respondents) in the form of their desires and expectations in carrying out their duties/jobs are supported by additional income allowances provided by the agency where they work as part of the compensation they receive and have a strong desire to play an active role in the organization where they work. work and are always willing to give something of a helping hand to the success and prosperity of the organization. Work motivation has a significant effect on the Work Commitment of the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. This means that the motivation from within (the respondent) is increasing in the form of their desires and expectations in carrying out their duties/work. Provision of Additional Employee Income (TPP) has a significant effect on the Work Commitment of the Regional

Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. This means that the higher the employee's perception of the additional income they receive from the agency where they work, it causes the involvement and emotional attachment of employees to their duties and work units to also increase. Organizational Commitment has no significant effect on the Work Commitment of the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province. This means that the desire of an employee to be able to survive as part of the agency where he works but does not increase his active role in his involvement in every activity carried out by his agency. In this study, there are several limitations when researchers conduct research, namely this study only uses cross-sectional data that is momentary, so the results of the study are not to be generalized in general. Then, this research is only focused on the Regional Personnel Agency of Southeast Sulawesi Province, so that in the future it can conduct research with a wider scope. For further researchers, it is recommended to add the independent variable of employee work discipline as a variable that can increase work commitment, because the model in this study is still possible to add other variables that affect work commitment.

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